

Description of obstacles in Development Women Entrepreneurs: In Haryana

Dr. Pinki Yadav

Assistant Professor in Geography, Vaish College, Rohtak

Corresponding author- **Dr. Pinki Yadav**

Email- 13pinkiyadav@gmail.com

Abstract

Women entrepreneurs have play a very important role in development of nation .But in coming days women entrepreneurs have to face many types of problems such as financial problem , communication , health issue , family problem , management system. The study concludes with a wide range of recommendations to promote a more enabling environment for women's entrepreneurship in India. Present paper is based on both Primary and Secondary source of data such as- questionnaire and govt. offices. The data analysis has been based on some effective tables and diagrams. Some major findings and fruitful suggestions for women entrepreneurs have been given in full paper.

Keywords: Women, Entrepreneurs, Enabling Environment.

Introduction

The term "social entrepreneurship" is being adopted and used more extensively, but its meaning is not widely understood. In particular, the scope of social entrepreneurship in both business and the voluntary sector has not been mapped effectively. This paper begins by defining social entrepreneurs and social entrepreneurship. Women's entrepreneurship encompasses self-employment, income generation, and the management of businesses/enterprises. In the area of women's entrepreneurship, and although government policies and promotion strategies have been giving new opportunities to women, few have come forward. According to the same Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) Annual Report 2011-12, only 13.72 per cent of enterprises in the registered MSME sector were enterprises managed by women, representing about 2.15 lakh (or 215,000 enterprises across the country). In today's era women entrepreneurs have a very crucial role to play. The only condition is that they get a good environment for development. But today our organisation society keeps women inside the boundary wall. Because of which she does not prove to be very effective in the role of development. In today's era, by providing financier facilities to women entrepreneurs and giving the knowledge of ICT, we can move forward a lot. Traditionally our society is the male dominant society, women do not have the same status as men. But in the modern society, women have started playing a decisive role in development, not limited to the four walls of the house. Women are attracted by the increasing quality of today's small and medium scale industries and are playing a good role in the development of the industry.

Objectives of the study:

1. The main objective of the present study was to know main obstacles face by women as entrepreneurs to start up their business.
2. Second objective of the study is to know the main barriers for Women Entrepreneurs as Compared Male Entrepreneurs.

Research Design

The present study was based on both sources of data collection. Almost information has been collected about the work is through the questionnaire. Primary data was collected from 60 entrepreneurs from 4 districts (Kurukshetra, Ambala , Yamunanagar ,Panchkula) in Haryana State. The most appropriate scope of the study were defined through a prior work of concern study.

Methodology

Data has been analysed after receiving information from primary and secondary sources in which some information has obtained from 60 entrepreneurs from 4 districts .After receiving the information from 4 districts the views given by the entrepreneurs have been analysed though statistical tools and techniques .

Data analysis and interpretation

Entrepreneurs have to face some problems in starting their problems. Some women have to their own industry keeping mind in financial problem, unemployment, for time consumed and some women join the industry to further their family business Some information has been obtained from entrepreneurs to start their business, which is analysed as follows;

Table1: Factors influencing business start-up

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Encouragement from family	06	10%
Sense of self achievement	13	21.67%
Profit-making aspirations	15	25%
No employment	04	6.67%
To pass time	02	3.33%
Financial need	17	28.33%
To continue in the family occupation	03	5%
Total	60	100%

Source: Based on Field Survey Table 1 explores the factor effecting the business start-up out of 60 entrepreneur's shows 28.23% shows that main factor influencing business start-up for financial need .while 25 % is for profit-making aspirations

and 21% woman work for their self-achievement and 10 encouragement from family and least factor influencing business start-up is to continue in the family occupation i.e.5%.

Table2: Additional Barriers for Women Entrepreneurs as Compared with Male Entrepreneurs

Additional Barriers	No. of Respondents	Percentage
No difference	02	3.33%
Access to finance & raw materials	21	35%
Knowledge of ICT	20	33.34%
Perception of women's capability	17	28.33%
Total	60	100%

Source: Based on Field Survey Table 2 reveals that main barrier for Women Entrepreneurs is access to finance & raw materials i.e.35% because as compare to man they face many difficulty in getting raw material and financial spot from the family while 33.34% entrepreneur believe that lack of ICT knowledge they face many kind of difficulties to start up their business and28.33% believe due to less

precipitation women entrepreneur's capability. So the main barriers for start-up for their business was lack of knowledge of ICT due to less interest and awareness of new technology and staying away from raw material and elaborate finical facility are the main barrier for woman entrepreneurs as compared with male entrepreneurs

Table3: Problems faced in accessing Government Schemes

Category	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Easy	08	13.33%
Neither Easy nor Difficult	25	41.67%
Difficult	27	45%
Total	60	100%

Source: Based on Field Survey

Fig 1 Problems faced in accessing Government Schemes

Table 3 & fig 1 reveals the problem faced by entrepreneur to receive the scheme provide by the government in which it was found that 45% woman entrepreneur conceded their respond says that it is difficult that the scheme that provide by the government while 41.67% says that it is neither easy nor difficult to access the scheme and only 13.3% considered it is very easy. This prove that woman entrepreneur face a lot of problem in getting the scheme from the government. It is need to improve the facilities for women for their better development

Major Findings

1. Financial Problem

In India women entrepreneurs have to face a lot of financial problem to start up their business. It is found that women entrepreneurs have faced many kind of problems such as, getting loans easily.

2. Non Availability of Raw Material

Raw material is most essential part to start up new business. It is the base of industry to start up business .Because without the raw material availability there is no use of human resource.

3. Lack knowledge in ICT

Knowledge of ICT is very essential for industrial development, but in Indian society very few entrepreneur has been knowledge about it.Indian women have to be deprived of it due to which they are not able to earn so much name in industry

4. male dominating society

In Indian society has always been male dominant society where is women have never been treated equal to the men equality has not been achieved. Women have always looked down upon by men, they have always been seen only as subordinate, which have been major problem for women

5. Procedural simplification

For women entrepreneur there is need to the procedures and formalities should be simplified for registration of business, financial legal assistance, subsidies, concessions, relief etc., from different government and nongovernmental departments.

6. Role of the state governments

State government should be offered soft loans and subsidies. Due to lack knowledge about it women cannot be benefited by raise funds through various schemes and incentives provided by the State Government. It should be provide some benefit schemes for women entrepreneur such as, Prime ministers RozgarYojana, The Khadi and Rural village industries scheme, etc. for betterment of development in industries

7. Role of Supporting Organizations

Another thing is find that there is a need for greater transparency and renewed efforts to increase awareness of existing regulations, and support mechanisms.

Training institutions should be provide for their staff, update their curricula, and facilities in line with the times and to better meet pressing and evolving demands.

It is suggested that NABARD and SIDBI take the initiative to draw the attention of the operating managements of the banks to create a potentially growing and profitable business segment. To overcome the technical deficiency at the branch level, the lead bank office in the district should establish a women cell to provide specialized assistance to all the branches.

8. Access to Market

There should most dominant factors of production, to productive assets and productive is markets. Marketing assistance should be developed by promoting linkages between women enterprises .it is also very important to have a proper market because without the market we cannot supply the market unless there is market knowledge that item not be sale able

9. Access to Infrastructure and social service

Government should provide to Implementation of infrastructure must be accompanied by the government women to in income-generating activities, including education, training and extra benefits such as child care facilities. Government should set some priorities for women entrepreneurs for allocation of industrial plots, sheds and basic infrastructure/amenities.

Some fruitful suggestion for successful women entrepreneur

1. Some important tips are as follows
2. To provide positive environment that can encourage move forward
3. Raising education movement and provide training the complete personality of women for develop c

Creating and conducting awareness programme foe development of women entrepreneur .Recognising the poetical of women inhumane their quality so they can start their business government should provide some intensive programme for women development to follows the above steps she becomes a good business women. For this the government and the journal public should to take better steps for the development of women entrepreneur so that women can make so their better development

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